

A new learning styles-based approach for analyzing and personalizing the learning content in online courses

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Abstract: Online courses have transformed modern education by offering flexible and accessible learning opportunities. However, adapting course content to the diverse learning preferences of students remains a key challenge. This study introduces a data-driven approach to personalize and analyze learning content in online courses based on the Felder-Silverman Learning Styles Model (FSLSM). The concept of “learning styles” is operationalized through four FSLSM dimensions, and “cognitive profiles” refer to learners’ behavioral patterns in processing and interacting with content. An experimental study was conducted with 40 first-year economics students at the University of Guelma (Algeria), divided into control and experimental groups. Both groups accessed the same initial learning materials, while the experimental group received FSLSM-adapted content in the post-test phase. The results suggest a positive effect of the personalized content on learners’ cognitive engagement and progression. This approach demonstrates the potential of integrating learning style analysis and adaptive content delivery in online learning environments.

Keywords: Course analysis, Course design, Personalized Content, Felder and Silverman Learning style, Online Course.

Categories: H.3.1, H.3.2, H.3.3, H.3.7, H.5.1

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1 Introduction

Online human learning environments play a pivotal role in modern education, offering flexibility and accessibility to diverse learners. Nevertheless, ensuring optimal learning performance in such contexts can be challenging due to various individual learning methods [Gulsecen, 13]. To address this issue, there is a growing need to incorporate adaptive pedagogical content based on learning styles [Kocoglu, 16]. Among the different learning style models, this study focuses on Felder and Silverman’s Learning Styles Model (FSLSM), due to its multidimensional structure and its suitability for online learning environments. Unlike other models such as VARK or Kolb, FSLSM addresses four dimensions of learning behavior that can be observed and interpreted through interaction data, making it particularly relevant for data-driven adaptation.

By leveraging the potential of technologies and utilizing models such as Felder and Silverman's Learning Styles Model (FSLSM), instructors can personalize instructional content to better align with learners' preferences and enhance their overall learning experience. This customized strategy not only fosters engagement and motivation but also optimizes the efficiency of online courses, eventually enhancing learning results and advocating for a more inclusive and student-centered online learning environment. Analysis methodologies have emerged as a promising solution to enhance the effectiveness of online human learning environments.

These strategies utilize technology and data-driven approaches to customize the learning experience in real-time, taking into account each learner's unique qualities and needs. Adaptive systems can personalize instructional content, learning activities, and assessments by analyzing various factors such as learning styles, preferences, performance data, and feedback. This adaptable method allows learners to interact with resources corresponding to their learning preferences, speed, and skill levels, promoting a more customized and effective learning experience. Moreover, adaptive methodologies empower instructors by providing them with real-time insights and recommendations, enabling them to make informed decisions and provide targeted support to learners. Through the integration of adaptive methodologies, online human learning environments have the potential to optimize learner engagement, promote self-directed learning, and ultimately improve learning outcomes.

On the other hand, identifying learners' learning styles has many advantages in education and training. Learning styles refer to the preferences of individual learners regarding how they prefer to receive and process information [Dangaiso, 22]. Understanding these preferences can help teachers adapt their teaching methods to meet learners' needs better [Alfaro, 18].

The existing online learning courses often fail to cater to the diverse learning styles of individual learners, which can hinder the effectiveness of the learning process and outcomes. Therefore, there is a need to develop an approach that enables teachers to adapt or personalize pedagogical content based on learners' learning styles in a human learning platform, thereby improving the learning outcomes of online courses. This problem statement highlights the issue of the lack of adaptation to learning styles in online courses. It emphasizes the need for a solution that enhances the alignment between instructional content and learners' preferences. Accordingly, the main objective of this study is to examine the impact of analyzing and adapting online course content based on FSLSM learning styles on students' cognitive development.

With this objective in mind, the following research inquiries can be formulated: What is the influence of analysis of pedagogical content based on learning styles, as proposed in this study, on the learning outcomes of online courses?

How can the preference scores for FSLSM dimensions be accurately computed for both instructional content and learners, facilitating the analysis process? What is the effectiveness of the comparative analysis between preference scores in identifying learning styles that are not supported by the pedagogical content but are supported by the learners? How do the learning outcomes of learners who receive analyzed instructional content based on their learning styles compare to those who receive non-analyzed content?

Our primary aim is to assist teachers in enhancing the learning outcomes of their online courses by analyzing pedagogical content based on learning styles within a human learning platform. This paper introduces a novel approach to analyzing and

personalizing instructional content based on Felder and Silverman's Learning Styles Model (FSLSM).

The following sections of this paper are structured as follows: Section 2 presents a comprehensive overview of related works. Section 3 delves into the design of the proposed system. Section 4 outlines the system's implementation and presents the results of the experiments. Lastly, Section 5 offers the concluding remarks of the paper and presents the future work.

2 Literature review

2.1 Felder and Silverman Learning Style Model (FSLSM)

This learning style model is often used in technology-assisted learning [Felder, 20]. It is generally preferred in a web-based learning environment [El Aissaoui, 19]. Furthermore, it is beneficial because of the four dimensions of learning style preferences that consider the technological aspects of e-learning learners [Muñoz, 98]. The four dimensions to categorize learners are [Felder, 20; El Aissaoui, 19; Muñoz, 98]:

- **Processing (Active/Reflective):** Active learners are themselves active, and their user activity in web environments is swift, while reflective learners think about concepts slowly, and their user activity in web environments is generally very slow.
- **Perception (Sensing/Intuitive):** Sensitive learners attempt to learn underlying facts, while intuitive learners prefer to identify relationships between concepts.
- **Input (Visual/Verbal):** Visual learners prefer to learn using pictures, flowcharts, and cartoons, while verbal learners tend to learn using textual representations.
- **Understanding (Sequential/Global):** Sequential learners learn in increments, while global learners learn simultaneously.

Figure 1: Conceptual scheme of FSLSM dimensions.

While other models such as VARK and Honey & Mumford exist, FSLSM was selected due to its multidimensional cognitive basis and its demonstrated applicability in adaptive web-based learning environments. The Felder and Silverman Learning

Style Model (FSLSM) was selected not only because of its multidimensional representation of learning preferences but also due to its strong compatibility with behavioral data that can be extracted from online learning platforms. Unlike models such as VARK or Kolb, which primarily depend on self-reported questionnaires, FSLSM allows mapping observable learner interactions such as navigation frequency, time spent on specific resources, and forum participation to its four dimensions. This capability makes it particularly suitable for data-driven analysis and adaptive systems aiming to provide real-time personalization. Furthermore, FSLSM's structure facilitates quantitative computation of preference scores, enabling the integration of fuzzy logic techniques used in this study for style representation.

2.2 Related works

Extensive research attention has been directed towards the automated recognition of students' learning styles, aiming to establish a personalized approach to learning.

Researchers have employed various methodologies in their quest to achieve this objective (see Table 1). For example, a literature review has highlighted the utilization of rule-based algorithms and Bayesian networks for the automated identification of learning styles. This approach holds the potential to enhance the delivery of adaptive learning content. Another review article [Sianturi, 22] emphasizes that numerous researchers incorporate students' personality traits as input to identify learning styles within adaptive learning environments. Furthermore, in an independent study [Kawale, 22], researchers used a tree-augmented naive Bayes network, which demonstrated higher precision in detecting learning styles than the Bayesian network.

In other research [Farooqui, 23], the proposal suggests employing fuzzy logic techniques and neural networks for learning styles detection. The authors report that implementing this approach enhances knowledge-management systems and e-learning effectiveness. Fuzzy logic has also been utilized in a separate study [Peng, 22] as a method for automated identification of learning styles. In this case, the input solely comprises the learner's navigational access data, which has given promising outcomes in terms of enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the overall learning process. Moreover, as indicated by additional studies [Alshmrany, 22; Essa, 23], learners' skills and prior knowledge have emerged as pivotal attributes employed in the automatic identification of learning styles. Both research projects concentrate on mapping students' skills, encompassing factual knowledge and their capacity to comprehend, integrate, and apply knowledge. These skills are closely interconnected with the concept of learning styles. [Balti, 23] conducted a study where they presented an automated approach for identifying students' learning styles using web usage mining. More specifically, the students' log files underwent classification by applying clustering algorithms to discern their learning styles.

In separate research [Rami, 22], four computational intelligence techniques were explored to improve the accuracy of learning styles detection: ant colony optimization, artificial neural network, particle swarm optimization, and genetic algorithm. This was accomplished by integrating the Fuzzy Sets-based Learning Style Model and analyzing the students' behavior. In a distinct investigation [Mehenaoui, 22], the authors introduced an inference engine that integrated a neural network and employed specific observed parameters of learners' behaviors to deduce their learning styles

Study Reference	Characteristics	Technology	Learning style
[Marosan, 22]	Learning behavior (visiting the forum, sending and receiving e-mails, watching videos, carrying out exercises, communicating, etc.)	Tree augmented naïve Bayesian network	FSLSM
[Munoz, 22]	Learners' interactions (content, forum, chat, etc.)	Neural networks and fuzzy logic	Honey and Mumford model
[Sianturi, 22]	Learners' navigational data	Fuzzy logic	Behavioral patterns
[Farooqui, 23]	Learners' cognitive skills	Fuzzy logic	Mental processing modelling
[Kawale, 22]	Prior Knowledge (knowledge of fact, knowledge of meaning, integration of knowledge, application of knowledge)	Rule-based association	VARL
[Peng, 22]	Web usage	Custer analysis	FSLSM
[Balti, 23]	Learners' behaviour	Artificial neural network, Genetic algorithm, Ant colony system, Particle swarm optimization	FSLSM
[Rami, 22]	Learners' behaviour	Artificial	Gardner's theory
[Pardamea, 22]	Learners' actions	Decision trees	FSLSM
[Essa,23]	Learners' behavior	Artificial neural network Machine Learning	FSLSM
[Meheanaoui, 22]	Learners' behavior, Behavioral Patterns	Learners' behavior, Behavioral Patterns	FSLSM

Table 1: Related Work

In contrast to the reviewed works, the approach proposed in this study is distinctive in two major aspects. First, while most existing studies focus on detecting learners' learning styles using behavioral data or psychometric tools, they often stop at classification without closing the loop toward content adaptation. Our approach goes further by not only identifying learners' preferences using behavioral indicators but also analyzing the instructional content itself using the same FSLSM dimensions. Second, unlike many existing works that apply FSLSM solely to learners, our method

establishes a bidirectional analysis that compares the FLSM-based profiles of both the learners and the learning materials. This comparison enables the detection of mismatches and supports precise personalization. Furthermore, we propose a fuzzy logic-based computation model to quantify and visualize these preferences, which enhances the interpretability and adaptability of the system. These elements together represent a novel and integrative methodology that bridges a crucial gap in personalized online learning systems.

Unlike most previous works that primarily focused on identifying learners' learning styles, the present study introduces a bidirectional analysis framework that considers both the learner and the instructional content. The originality of our approach lies in quantifying preference scores for each FLSM dimension on both sides, content and learner, and then comparing these values to detect mismatches. This dual perspective enables a more comprehensive understanding of how well the pedagogical design supports learners' styles. Furthermore, by integrating fuzzy logic techniques, the system allows for a continuous representation of learning style compatibility rather than relying on static classifications. This methodological distinction marks a significant advancement over prior research, which generally treated learning styles as fixed attributes independent of content design.

3 Proposed approach

The primary objective of this study is to explore the integration of the Felder and Silverman Learning Styles Model (FLSM) in the design and personalization of online courses through the analysis of learning content. FLSM was chosen due to its comprehensive representation of learner preferences across multiple cognitive dimensions, which makes it particularly well-suited for adaptive learning environments. Specifically, this research introduces a novel approach for examining instructional material through the lens of FLSM, aiming to enhance alignment between content presentation and individual learning styles.

The proposed approach relies on doing a comparative analysis of the preference scores of the FLSM dimensions for both the learning content and the learners.

The preference scores for the learning content are determined based on the extent to which the FLSM dimensions are utilized in the online course design. In parallel, the learners' preference scores are calculated through the analysis of their learning behaviors across multiple FLSM dimensions. Rather than assigning each learner a single, fixed style, our approach captures a combination of style preferences by computing continuous preference degrees using fuzzy logic. This allows us to reflect the natural variability and multidimensionality of learning preferences, which may vary by subject or context. Furthermore, we are aware that some learning styles may be less effectively supported in online environments (e.g., kinesthetic). Therefore, the system focuses on dimensions that can be realistically addressed within digital learning platforms, such as active-reflective or visual-verbal, ensuring practical applicability for instructors."

The research work aims to help the teacher personalize the course content and determine the level of support in a course for specific learning styles based on the FLSM.

This approach uses the latter to identify the match between the learning content and the learners to improve learners' learning outcomes. Figure 2 illustrates the system's general architecture that adopts the proposed approach.

Figure 2: General system architecture

3.1 Data collection process

In our study, the data collection process plays a central role in bridging the gap between learners' interactions and the analysis of their learning styles based on FLSM. Data were collected through an e-learning platform developed specifically for this experiment, which logs detailed learner interactions with various pedagogical elements of the online course.

For each learner, the system automatically recorded behavioral data such as the number of visits, time spent, and actions taken on each conceptual element of the learning object (e.g., Resume, Outline, Definitions, Examples, Illustrations, Exercises, Forums, Self-Assessments, and Additional Reading Materials). This interaction data was stored in a structured format (database logs) for each learning session.

These data points serve as indicators to infer learners' preferences across the four FLSM dimensions (Processing, Perception, Input, and Understanding), as detailed in Section 3.5. The tools used for this process include logging modules embedded in the learning management system (LMS), timestamp tracking, and user event counters.

By analyzing these logged behaviors through the metrics described in Tables 3 and 4, we calculated the learners' FLSM dimension preferences using a fuzzy logic-based model. This approach enabled a data-driven and scalable method of estimating learning styles without the need for manual questionnaires.

The automatically collected data comprising time spent on learning objects, frequency of visits, and specific learner actions serve as the foundation for the

subsequent analytical process. Each variable is normalized and mapped to the corresponding FLSM dimensions (Processing, Perception, Input, and Understanding). For instance, frequent interactions with exercises or forums indicate preferences aligned with active processing, whereas extended reading time on definitions or summaries reflects reflective or verbal tendencies. These mapped indicators are then used to construct the learner's preference vectors and to compare them with content-based vectors, enabling the fuzzy logic model to compute compatibility scores between learners and learning objects.

3.2 Course structure

In this study, the online course is structured as a sequence of modular learning objects (LOs), each representing a semantically coherent instructional unit that addresses a specific topic within the "General Computer Science" subject indicated by the formula (1).

$$Course = \bigcup_{i=1}^N LearningObject_i \quad (1)$$

Each LO includes a predefined set of conceptual elements: Resume, Outline, Definition, Example, Illustration, Exercise, Discussion Forum, Self-Assessment, and Additional Reading Resources. These elements were defined based on best practices in instructional design and grounded in alignment with the FLSM dimensions, as detailed in Section 3.3.

The LOs are connected through a prerequisite relationship, requiring learners to successfully complete self-assessments before proceeding to the next object, ensuring a progressive learning path.

While the current implementation of the LOs was tailored to the needs of the experimental study, the structure adheres to principles compatible with IEEE Learning Object Metadata (LOM) standards. Each learning object is associated with descriptive metadata fields, such as title, description, learning objectives, interactivity type, format, and difficulty level, allowing for future interoperability.

Although full SCORM (Sharable Content Object Reference Model) compliance was not implemented in the prototype version used for this research, the learning objects were designed with SCORM-like modularity in mind, enabling reusability, portability, and potential integration into SCORM-compliant LMSs with minimal adjustments.

Future iterations of this system will incorporate SCORM packaging to enhance compatibility across platforms and facilitate broader adoption in institutional e-learning environments.

In addition to ensuring interoperability, this structured representation also facilitates the analytical process used in this study. The explicit metadata fields (such as interactivity type and difficulty level) are automatically mapped to FLSM dimensions, enabling the system to identify how each learning object supports specific learner preferences. This connection between standardized metadata and adaptive analysis strengthens the practical relevance of the proposed framework.

3.3 Relationship between FLSM dimensions and learning object

In this approach, we have established a relationship between the dimensions described in Silverman's model and the specific design elements of the learning object. This

strategic link is based on previous research, which allows us to strategically align the characteristics associated with each learning style dimension with the corresponding attributes and characteristics present in the design of the learning object (see Table 2).

Conceptual elements of the learning object	Processing		Perception		Input		Understanding	
	Active	Reflective	Sensing	Intuitive	Visual	Verbal	Sequential	Global
Resume							-	+
Outline							+	-
Definition	-	+	-	+				
Example	-	+	+	-				
Illustration	+	-	+	-	+	-		
Exercise	+	-	+	-				
Discussion	+	-			-	+		
Forum								
Self-Assessment	+	-	+	-				
Additional Reading Resources	-	+	-	+	-	+		

+ Support the degree of preference for learning style.

- Does not support the degree of learning style preference.

Empty field: There is no relationship with the learning style.

Table 2: Proposed relationships between conceptual elements of learning object and dimensions of FSLSM [Mehenaoui, 22]

3.4 Indicators of learning content analysis

Based on the proposed relationship between the FSLSM dimensions and the learning object table 2 (section 3.3), we have proposed a set of indicators to be used to calculate degrees of preference for each FSLSM dimension at the level of the learning object table 3.

In Table 2, we proposed a relationship between the proposed set of metrics and FSLSM dimensions at the learning object level (Table A.1), Appendix A.

Conceptual Elements of the learning objects	Characteristic	Measure	Description
Resume	<i>Resume-Availability</i>	Boolean	Is there a resume for the learning object?
Outline	<i>Outline-Availability</i>	Boolean	Is there an outline for the learning object?
Definition	<i>Definition-Availability</i>	Boolean	Are there definitions on the learning object?
	<i>Definition-Frequency</i>	Count	The number of definitions in the learning object.
Example	<i>Example-Availability</i>	Boolean	Are there examples on the learning object?
	<i>Example-Frequency</i>	Count	The number of examples in the learning object.

Conceptual Elements of the learning objects	Characteristic	Measure	Description
Illustration	<i>Illustration-Availability</i>	Boolean	Are there illustrations on the learning object?
	<i>Illustration-Frequency</i>	Count	The number of illustrations in the learning object.
Exercise	<i>Exercise-Availability</i>	Boolean	Are there exercises on the learning object?
	<i>Exercise-Frequency</i>	Count	The number of exercises in the learning object.
Discussion Forum	<i>Forum-Availability</i>	Boolean	Are there forums on the learning object?
	<i>Forum-Frequency</i>	Count	The number of forums in the learning object.
Self-Assessment	<i>Self-Ass--Availability</i>	Boolean	Are there Self-Assessments on the learning object?
	<i>Self-Ass-Frequency</i>	Count	The number of Self-Assessments in the learning object.
Additional Reading Resources	<i>Add-R-Res-Availability</i>	Boolean	
	<i>Add-R-Res -Frequency</i>	Count	

Table 3: Proposed indicators for analyzing the learning content

3.5 Indicators of identifying learners' learning styles

In this section, we try to answer question 2 posed in the introduction: To what extent are each of the dimensions of the Felder and Silverman learning style model supported by learners?

We proposed indicators for calculating learners' degrees of preference for each FLSM dimension from table 2 (section 3.3).

Conceptual Elements of the learning objects	Behaviors	Measure	Description
Resume	<i>Resume-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits the resume
	<i>Resume-Stay</i>	Time	Time spent (in seconds) on the resume
Outline	<i>Outline-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits the outline
	<i>Outline-Stay</i>	Time	Time spent (in seconds) on the outline

Conceptual Elements of the learning objects	Behaviors	Measure	Description
Definition	<i>Definition-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits the definitions Time spent (in seconds) on definitions
	<i>Definition-Stay</i>	Time	
Example	<i>Example-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits the examples. Time spent (in seconds) on the examples
	<i>Example-Stay</i>	Time	
Illustration	<i>Illustration-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits the illustrations. Time spent (in seconds) on illustrations
	<i>Illustration-Stay</i>	Time	
Exercise	<i>Exercise-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits the exercises. Time spent (in seconds) on exercises
	<i>Exercise-Stay</i>	Time	
Discussion Forum	<i>Forum-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits the forums. Number of times the learner posts a message in a forum. Time spent (in seconds) on the forums.
	<i>Exercise-Post</i>	Count	
	<i>Forum-Stay</i>	Time	
Self-Assessment	<i>Self-Ass-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits a self-assessment. Time spent (in seconds) on self-assessment. If the learner tests the self-assessment.
	<i>Self-Ass-Stay</i>	Time	
	<i>Seil-Ass-Test</i>	Boolean	
Additional Reading Resources	<i>Add-R-Res-Visit</i>	Count	Number of times the learner visits the Additional Reading Resources. Time spent (in seconds) on self-assessment.
	<i>Add-R-Res -Stay</i>	Time	

Table 4: Proposed indicators to calculate FSLSM preference level for learner

From Table 4, we proposed a relationship between the set of proposed behaviors and the FSLSM dimensions for learners.

3.6 Proposed model of FSLSM dimensions

From Table A.1 (section Appendix A) and Table B.1 (section Appendix B), we constructed two types of vectors (see Figure 4).

3.6.1 Threshold Vector

This vector includes the thresholds of the proposed metrics for each of the FSLSM dimensions. So, we have the threshold vectors for the learning object on one side and the threshold vectors for the learners on the other side, as follows:

For the learning object

In the proposed approach, to construct the threshold vectors for the learning object, we need to set the *ThresholdFrequency* value, which represents the maximum value of the frequency feature in Table 3, as follows:

$$ThresholdFrequency = Max\{ElementFrequency_i\}_{(i \in 1..N)} \quad (2)$$

For the learner

In this approach, to construct the threshold vectors for the learner, we need to set the *ThresholdVisit*, *ThresholdStay*, and *ThresholdPost* values that represent the maximum values of the visit, time spent, and post message behaviors in Table 3, as follows:

$$ThresholdVisit = Max\{ElementVisit_i\}_{(i \in 1..N)} \quad (3)$$

$$ThresholdStay = Max\{ElementStay_i\}_{(i \in 1..N)} \quad (4)$$

$$ThresholdPost = Max\{ElementPost_i\}_{(i \in 1..N)} \quad (5)$$

N: is the number of conceptual elements composing the learning object.

3.6.2 Vector Metrics

This type of vector includes the values of the proposed metrics for each of the FSLSM dimensions. So, we have the metric vectors for the learning object on one side and the metric vectors for the learners on the other side. Figure 4 illustrates the two types of vectors. For each dimension we have:

- A threshold vector of dimension i for LS1 characterized by 0.
- A threshold vector of dimension i for LS2 characterized by 1.
- A metric vector (for a learning object and learners) of dimension i characterized by normalized values in the interval [0; 1].

Figure 3: Proposed model for the FSLSM dimensions

3.7 Fuzzy logic model for FSLSM preference calculation

The objective is to calculate the degrees of preference of the dimensions of the FSLSM for the learning object and the learners. We have proposed a computational model based on fuzzy logic techniques. The proposed fuzzy logic model allows the calculation of the degrees of preference of the dimensions of the FSLSM for the learning object and the learners (because both are the same data structure in the context of FSLSM).

3.7.1 Calculation of the similarity

To calculate the similarity between the metric vector and the two threshold vectors for LS1 and LS2 of dimension i ($i \in 1..4$) of the FSLSM, we used the Manhattan distance:

$$d(A, B)_i = |X_B - X_A| + |Y_B - Y_A| \tag{6}$$

Such as A and B, two vectors of respective coordinates (X_A, Y_A) and (X_B, Y_B) .

The Manhattan distance was selected in our proposed approach due to its suitability for high-dimensional and normalized data, which is the case in our system where feature vectors representing FSLSM dimensions are derived from counts and time-based behavioral indicators, all normalized within the range [0,1]. Unlike Euclidean distance, which emphasizes large individual deviations due to squaring terms, Manhattan distance aggregates absolute differences in a linear way, which preserves proportionality and reduces sensitivity to outliers. Additionally, since the input features (visits, durations, frequencies) in our analysis are not strictly orthogonal or continuous in nature but rather represent interpretable behavioral attributes, the use of Manhattan

distance aligns better with semantic comparisons across FSLSM categories. Prior research in adaptive learning environments and recommender systems [e.g., Muñoz 2022; Mehenaoui 2022] has shown that Manhattan distance provides effective results in comparing user preference profiles, especially in fuzzy or categorical decision-making contexts. Although other metrics such as Euclidean or Minkowski could be employed, we chose Manhattan distance for its simplicity, computational efficiency, and interpretability within the context of fuzzy logic-based classification. Future work may include a comparative study evaluating the impact of different distance metrics on learning style alignment and recommendation effectiveness.

3.7.2 Classification process

In our approach, we were inspired by some works to define two categories for each dimension of the FSLSM as follows:

- LS1Degr: The degree of preference (level of support) of learning style 1 of dimension i.
- LS2Degr: The degree of preference (level of support) of learning style 2 of dimension i.

Identification of membership functions Before defining the membership functions, we defined the range of distance values.

- The learning style 1 LS1 threshold vector is characterized by zeros.
- The learning style 2 LS2 threshold vector is characterized by ones.
- *DistanceMax*: The Manhattan distance between the Vector Threshold LS1 characterized by zeros and the Vector Threshold LS2 characterized by ones.
- *d_i*: The distance between the metric vector and the threshold vector of the learning style of dimension i.

In the proposed approach, the degrees of preference of the FSLSM dimensions for each learning style are the degrees of truth obtained by the membership functions of the proposed fuzzy logic model.

Example 1. For Dimension 1: Processing (you can see Formulas 7, 8, and 9 and Figure 5).

$$\mathbf{u}_{Active}(d)_i = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{Si } 0 \leq d_i \leq 1/5DistanceMax \\ 1 - \frac{d_i - 1/5DistanceMax}{4/5DistanceMax - 1/5DistanceMax}; & \text{Si } 1/5DistanceMax < d_i < 4/5DistanceMax \\ 0; & \text{Si } d_i \geq 4/5DistanceMax \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{Reflective}(d)_i = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{Si } d_i \leq 1/5DistanceMax \\ \frac{d_i - 1/5DistanceMax}{4/5DistanceMax - 1/5DistanceMax}; & \text{Si } 1/5DistanceMax < d_i < 4/5DistanceMax \\ 0; & \text{Si } 4/5DistanceMax \leq d_i \leq DistanceMax \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{Active}(d)_i + \mathbf{u}_{Reflective}(d)_i = 1 \tag{9}$$

Figure 4: Representation of membership functions for the processing dimension (active/reflective)

Example 2.

The following is an example of the proposed method for matching learning content and learners based on preference scores for the FSLSM dimensions. To show the degree of preference of the FSLSM dimensions for the learner and the learning content, it is first necessary to extract the standard values of the different indicators that each learner performs in the learning process (see Figures 6,7, and 8).

The learning object and dimension of the felder and silverman learning styles model.

Figure 5: Preference degrees of FSLSM dimensions for a learning object

Figure 6: Preference degrees of FSLSM dimensions for learners

Figure 7: Correspondence between preference degrees of FSLSM dimensions of learning object and learners

3.8 Visualization and Intervention Process

We recognize that many instructors may lack the specialized training or time required to implement complex learning style-based adaptations. To address this challenge, our

system provides intuitive and actionable visualizations that guide teachers toward feasible modifications, such as adding visual elements, supplementary readings, or discussion activities. These recommendations are generated automatically, requiring minimal prior expertise in instructional design. In doing so, the system serves not only as an analysis tool but also as a practical decision support system that empowers instructors to apply differentiated instruction without extensive retraining or additional resources.

The system also flags individual learners whose styles may require alternate materials or activities to support their needs. For example, highly verbal learners taking a course with few discussion forums and text resources may be flagged for the instructor. Using these visualizations, instructors can adapt course materials and learning activities to better align with the learning styles. For example, the instructor can add more visual aids for highly visual learners, incorporate additional case studies and real-world examples for sensing learners, and create peer discussion groups for verbal learners. Although the fuzzy logic-based model successfully represents learning styles, certain styles remain inherently less compatible with online learning environments. For instance, verbal learners typically require rich linguistic interaction and verbal feedback, which are often limited in asynchronous systems. When such learners are detected, the system recommends adding text-based forums, peer discussions, or short synchronous chat sessions to enhance verbal engagement. Similarly, global learners, who prefer to understand the overall picture before engaging with specific details, may experience difficulties in sequential course structures. In these cases, the system proposes the inclusion of concept maps, course overviews, and integrative assessments linking multiple modules. These concrete examples illustrate how the model mitigates style content mismatches by generating adaptive recommendations tailored to less-supported learner profiles in digital environments.

3.9 Proposed recommendation

To close identified gaps between course content and learners' learning styles, the system provides personalized recommendations focused on:

Learning resources:

- Suggesting specific alternate content formats (e.g., more visualizations, animations, and illustrations) for highly visual learners.
- Recommending more case studies, real-world examples, and hands-on activities for sensing learners' type.
- Proposing additional reading materials with textual explanations for verbal learners.

Engagement Channels

- Incorporating interactive discussion boards and forums for verbal learners craving more discourse.
- Creating peer chat groups for collaborative team projects suiting active learners.
- Establishing reflection blogs or journals for reflective learners desiring more introspective outlets.

Grouping and Events

- Forming study groups matching learners with complementary style preferences.
- Scheduling hands-on workshops led by instructors aligned with sensing and active styles.
- Organizing guest speaker sessions tailored to less supported dimensions (e.g., a verbal-focused guest for highly visual learners).

Overall, the recommendations focus on ways to modify instructional materials, learning activities, and engagement channels to create an experience personalized to learners' styles. They are explicitly generated in areas where gaps occur between content dimensions and learner needs.

3.10 Illustrative Example of System Application

To illustrate how the proposed recommendation process operates in practice, consider a learner identified through the fuzzy logic mechanism as having a visual–active learning style profile according to the FSLSM dimensions. During the content analysis phase, one learning object entitled “Introduction to Economic Models” was characterized as predominantly verbal–reflective, since its resources consisted mainly of textual explanations and analytical readings. When comparing the learner's and content's style vectors, the compatibility score generated by the fuzzy model was low (0.38).

Based on this result, the system automatically suggested pedagogical adaptations for the instructor, including the integration of conceptual diagrams, short interactive simulations, and brief self-assessment quizzes. These elements aimed to enhance visual engagement and promote active participation without altering the conceptual depth of the material. The instructor reviewed these suggestions and confirmed their pedagogical relevance for improving learner engagement.

This example demonstrates how the system translates analytical outcomes into actionable teaching recommendations, linking the theoretical model with real instructional practice. It also highlights the system's capacity to adapt learning content dynamically based on detected mismatches between learner and content profiles.

4 Experiment: Results and Discussion

We conducted two experimental tests to validate our proposals at the University of Guelma (Algeria). The objective of the experiments was to verify the impact of analyzing and personalizing the learning content based on the learners' learning styles on improving the cognitive profile of learners.

In this first experiment, we want to test the progression of the knowledge level (the cognitive profile) with two samples of learners. The learners of the first group used the learning management system (AnalyLS) with the application of the proposed approach. In contrast, the learners of the second group did not use the proposed learning style-based learning content analysis and personalized approach.

4.1 Participants

A set of 40 first-year undergraduate students from the Economics department were randomly chosen for the experiment. The selected students were divided into two groups: a control group and a test group. Each group contains 20 students. The first group (the control group) works without the proposed analysis approach, while the second group works with the developed analysis approach.

4.2 Methodology

We conducted an experimental study (test/control group) with the randomly selected students. To observe the impact of the suggested approach on the test group (TG) and compare it with the control group (CG), which did not use the suggested approach, we divided the students into two independent groups. Students in their first year of university study in the economics department have followed the concepts of the "General Computer Science" subject online.

This subject is divided into four learning objects based on the course structure of our e-learning system. All learning objects include a self-assessment, whose score is calculated by the formula (10).

$$Score_{evaluation(i)} = \frac{CorrectQuestionNumber}{TotalNumberQuestions} \quad (10)$$

During the experiment's first phase, the learners (test/control group) completed learning objects 1 and 2 (pre-test). To assess the cognitive profiles of each k learner's learning objects, we applied the formula (11).

$$PretestScore_{(k)} = \frac{Score_{evaluation(1)} + Score_{evaluation(2)}}{2} \quad (11)$$

For instance, within the second phase of the experiment and for the test group, learners classified as visual were provided with diagrammatic representations of key concepts, whereas verbal learners received equivalent textual explanations. Similarly, active learners were encouraged to engage with interactive exercises, while reflective learners completed short self-assessment questions. These examples illustrate how the experimental adaptation aligned with FSLSM dimensions without altering the conceptual content.

At the end of the second phase of the experiment, we will conduct a post-test. To assess the cognitive profiles of each learner k on his learning objects 3 and 4, we applied the formula (12).

$$PostestScore_{(k)} = \frac{Score_{evaluation(3)} + Score_{evaluation(4)}}{2} \quad (12)$$

This second test's objective is to evaluate the effect of the learning content analysis approach on improving learners' cognitive profiles.

Table 5 and Figure 9 present some statistics on the cognitive profiles of learners in the two groups.

Control group				Test group			
N 20	Pre-test	Post-test	Progression	N 20	Pre-test	Post-test	Progression
Min :	2,19	3,69	-0,1	Min :	2,01	7,225	1,96
1st Qu :	3,58875	4,5375	0,29875	1st Qu :	3,03375	7,7725	3,2675
Median :	4,095	4,8425	0,575	Median :	4,1525	8,01	4,4625
Mean :	4,18125	4,91875	0,7375	Mean :	3,982	8,16575	4,18375
3rd Qu :	4,6025	5,25875	1,3225	3rd Qu :	4,4975	8,6725	4,96625
Max :	5,895	5,865	1,61	Max :	6,705	9,29	6

Table 5: Statistics about the two groups

Figure 8: Differences in the means of the pre-test and post-test values for CG and TG

The null hypothesis is:

- H0: The proposed learning content analysis approach does not improve learners’ cognitive profiles.
- H1: The proposed learning content analysis approach helps learners improve their cognitive profiles.

To test our research hypothesis, we calculated the difference between the cognitive levels of learners from the two groups. We used the IBM SPSS Statistics statistical processing and analysis software for this test.

Before using the t-test, it must be ensured that the data is normally distributed. To do this, we used the Kolmogorov-Smirnova and Shapiro-Wilk tests. The results obtained showed that the data are distributed according to the normal law (Figure 10 and Figure 11). These results are expressed in Table 6.

Progression	Group	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistics	ddl	Sig.	Statistics	ddl	Sig.
n	Control	,175	20	,112	,937	20	,207
	Test	,175	20	,108	,959	20	,528

Table 6: Kolmogorov-Smirnova and Shapiro-Wilk normality tests

Figure 9: Distribution of progress values for the control group

Figure 10: Distribution of progression values for the test group

In the experimental setup, both the control group and the experimental (test) group had access to identical learning content during the pre-test phase (i.e., Learning Objects 1 and 2). This ensured a baseline cognitive profile for each learner and eliminated any initial bias stemming from content variation. In the post-test phase (i.e., Learning Objects 3 and 4), the control group continued to receive the standard, non-personalized version of the course content, while the experimental group received an adapted version of the same learning objects. The adaptation was performed based on the computed FLSM preference scores using behavioral indicators collected during the pretest. Specifically, the adaptation focused on increasing or modifying certain elements within the learning object (e.g., more visual aids for visual learners, added discussion forums

for verbal learners, additional examples for sensing learners, and so on). It is important to emphasize that the core content and learning objectives remained unchanged between both groups. Only the format and distribution of conceptual elements within the learning objects were adjusted in the experimental group, with the goal of aligning content delivery more closely with individual learning preferences. Regarding the potential influence of content complexity on learning outcomes, the selected subject, "General Computer Science," for first-year economics students was intentionally chosen due to its moderate conceptual difficulty and uniformity across modules. The course content was validated by three instructional designers to ensure equivalence in complexity and cognitive demand between the pre-test and post-test phases. While it is acknowledged that adapting the content format may introduce subtle differences beyond learning style alignment (e.g., improved clarity, engagement), the experimental design attempted to control for such effects by isolating format-based adaptations rather than altering the conceptual content itself.

Both groups completed the same pre-test using identical learning materials and assessment items to ensure baseline equivalence. During the post-test phase, the conceptual content remained identical for both groups; however, for the experimental group, the learning objects were adapted in their presentation format according to the learners' FLSM profiles. These adaptations included adding visual diagrams, interactive elements, or extended textual explanations when appropriate. Importantly, the cognitive complexity and difficulty level of the learning materials did not change.

During the experimental phase, the adaptive recommendations generated by the system were applied directly by the instructor within the course platform. For example, in response to detected mismatches, instructors added text-based discussion forums to support verbal learners, integrated concept maps and summary overviews for global learners, and introduced interactive quizzes for active learners. The instructors also reported that these targeted adjustments enhanced student engagement and improved the alignment between content presentation and learner preferences.

Nevertheless, future studies should explore more granular controls and alternative instructional contexts to further validate this approach.

4.3 Results and discussion

The t-test results are shown in Table 7. Based on the results obtained, a significant difference was observed ($t_{score} = 11.469$, $P_{value} = 0.002$) with 95% confidence. In addition, a significant difference was found between the means of progression of the control group (mean = 0.812; SD = 0.700) and the progression of the test group (mean = 4.183; SD = 1.112). As a result, the difference is improved significantly. Therefore, the null hypothesis H0 can be rejected in favor of hypothesis H1, supporting that the proposed approach improved the cognitive level of the learners.

Situation	N	df	Mean	SD	t_{Score}	Sig.
Control group	20	19	0.812	0,700	11.469	0.002
Test group	20	19	4,183	1,112		

Table 7: Testing of independent samples (Control/Test Group)

4.4 Limitations and Reproducibility

While the proposed approach demonstrates promising results, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations that may affect the generalizability and reproducibility of the findings.

First, the sample size was limited to 40 participants, all of whom were first-year economics students at the University of Guelma. Although the selection was randomized and balanced across control and test groups, the homogeneity of the population (academic level, disciplinary background, and digital exposure) may limit the applicability of the results to broader or more diverse learning contexts.

Second, the learning content used in the experiment was limited to an introductory-level "General Computer Science" course. The nature of the subject, mainly conceptual with a moderate level of complexity, may influence how learners react to style-based adaptation. Thus, further studies involving various academic disciplines and cognitive loads are needed to validate the model's robustness.

Third, although the proposed system incorporates a fuzzy logic-based computational model and structured tracking of learner behavior, the experimental design did not include a long-term follow-up to assess retention, nor did it consider learners' individual motivation or prior knowledge as confounding factors.

Therefore, the external validity of the study remains context dependent. Future research will address these limitations by expanding the sample size, testing the system in multiple domains, and integrating learner profiling mechanisms that account for motivation and background knowledge.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

The growing prevalence of online courses has revolutionized modern education, offering unprecedented flexibility and accessibility. However, ensuring optimal learning outcomes in these diverse environments remains a formidable challenge due to individual learners' wide range of learning styles. This study addressed this issue by introducing a novel approach to analyzing and personalizing pedagogical content based on the Felder and Silverman Learning Styles Model (FSLSM), intending to tailor learning materials to better align with learners' preferences and enhance their learning experience.

The results of the conducted experiment clearly showed that this strategy is highly beneficial in enhancing learners' cognitive profiles. The effects were notably positive, as learners provided with assessed and adjusted content based on their learning styles showed superior learning results compared to those who did not receive such tailored content. Moreover, our accurate computation of FSLSM preference scores for both learning materials and learners facilitated the identification of potential mismatches, enabling targeted interventions.

The implications of this research are far-reaching, as it offers a data-driven solution to create more personalized online learning environments. By leveraging adaptive technologies and personalizing content to individual learning styles, educators can foster increased student engagement, motivation, and self-directed learning. This personalized approach enhances the efficiency of online courses and encourages a fair

and inclusive educational experience for all learners, irrespective of their preferences or backgrounds.

While the current study yielded promising results, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations. The sample size was small, and the experiment was conducted within a specific academic domain. Future research should explore the scalability of this approach across larger and more diverse learner populations and its applicability in different educational contexts. Additionally, investigating the long-term effects of this approach on learning retention and achievement could provide valuable insights for further refinement and improvement.

Looking ahead, integrating this learning style-based content analysis approach with adaptive learning systems and learning analytics tools holds significant potential. By combining the power of data-driven personalization with real-time monitoring and feedback mechanisms, educators could gain deeper insights into learners' needs and continuously optimize the learning experience.

In conclusion, this study represents a significant step towards addressing the diverse learning needs of learners in online learning environments. By leveraging the power of data analysis and learning style models, we can, as future works, create more inclusive and effective online learning environments, ultimately fostering a more equitable and engaging educational experience for all. Furthermore, as technology continues to reshape the landscape of education, it is crucial to embrace innovative approaches that prioritize learner personalization, ensuring that no learner is left behind in the pursuit of knowledge and academic success.

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Appendix A.

Dimension	Learning style	Characteristic used	Proposed metric	Proposed thresholds LS1 (Supported by 0)	Proposed thresholds LS2 (Supported by 1)	
Processing	LS1 :Active	Illustration Availability	0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1	
		Illustration Frequency	$1 - (\text{Illustration Frequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1	
		ExerciseAvailability	0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1	
		Exercise Frequency	$1 - (\text{Exercise Frequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1	
		ForumAvailability	0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1	
		ForumFrequency	$1 - (\text{ForumFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1	
		Self-AssAvailability	0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1	
		Self-AssFrequency	$1 - (\text{Self-AssFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1	
	LS2 :Reflective	DefinitionAvailability	1 (exists) or 0 (does not exist)	0	1	
		DefinitionFrequency	$\text{DefinitionFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	0	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	
		ExampleAvailability	1 (exists) or 0 (does not exist)	0	1	
		ExampleFrequency	$\text{ExampleFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	0	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	
		Add-R-ResAvailability	1 (exists) or 0 (does not exist)	0	1	
		Add-R-ResFrequency	$\text{Add-R-ResFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	0	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	
	Perception	LS1 :Sensing	ExampleAvailability	0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1
			ExampleFrequency	$1 - (\text{ExampleFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1
IllustrationAvailability			0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1	
IllustrationFrequency			$1 - (\text{IllustrationFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1	
ExerciseAvailability			0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1	
ExerciseFrequency			$1 - (\text{ExerciseFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1	
LS2 :Intuitive		ExampleAvailability	0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1	
		ExampleFrequency	$1 - (\text{ExampleFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1	
		DefinitionAvailability	1 (exists) or 0 (does not exist)	0	1	
		DefinitionFrequency	$\text{DefinitionFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	0	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	
Add-R-ResAvailability	1 (exists) or 0 (does not exist)	0	1			
	Add-R-ResFrequency	$\text{Add-R-ResFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	0	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$		
	Input	LS1 :Visual	IllustrationAvailability	0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1
			IllustrationFrequency	$1 - (\text{IllustrationFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$
LS2 :Verbal	ForumAvailability	1 (exists) or 0 (does not exist)	0	1		
	ForumFrequency	$\text{ForumFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	0	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$		
	Add-R-ResAvailability	1 (exists) or 0 (does not exist)	0	1		
	Add-R-ResFrequency	$\text{Add-R-ResFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	0	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$		
Understanding	LS1 :Sequential	OutlineAvailability	0 (exists) or 1 (does not exist)	0	1	
		OutlineFrequency	$1 - (\text{OutlineFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	$1 - (\text{SeuilFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency})$	1	
	LS2 :Global	ResumeAvailability	1 (exists) or 0 (does not exist)	0	1	
ResumeFrequency		$\text{ResumeFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$	0	$\text{ThresholdFrequency} / \text{ThresholdFrequency}$		

Table A.1: Proposed data to compute FSLSM preference degrees at the learning object level.

Appendix B.

Dimension	Learning style	Behaviors	Proposed metric	Proposed thresholds LS1 (Supported by 0)	Proposed thresholds LS2 (Supported by 1)	
Processing	LS1 :Active	IllustrationVisit	$1 - (\text{IllustrationVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	1	
		IllustrationStay	$1 - (\text{IllustrationStay} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdTimeSpent} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent})$	1	
		ExerciseVisit	$1 - (\text{ExerciseVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	1	
		ExerciseStay	$1 - (\text{ExerciseStay} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdTimeSpent} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent})$	1	
		ForumVisit	$1 - (\text{ForumVisit} / \text{ThresholdPost})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdPost} / \text{ThresholdPost})$	1	
		ForumPost	$1 - (\text{ForumPost} / \text{ThresholdPost})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdPost} / \text{ThresholdPost})$	1	
		ForumStay	$1 - (\text{ForumStay} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdTimeSpent} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent})$	1	
		Self-AssTest	0 (existe) ou 1 (n'existe pas)	0	1	
		Self-AssVisit	$1 - (\text{Self-AssVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	1	
	Self-AssStay	$1 - (\text{Self-AssStay} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdTimeSpent} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent})$	1		
	LS2 :Reflective	DefinitionVisit	$\text{DefinitionVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	0	$\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	
		DefinitionStay	$\text{DefinitionStay} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent}$	0	$\text{ThresholdTimeSpent} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent}$	
		ExampleVisit	$\text{ExampleVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	0	$\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	
		ExampleStay	$\text{ExampleStay} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent}$	0	$\text{ThresholdTimeSpent} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent}$	
		Add-R-ResVisit	$\text{Add-R-ResVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	0	$\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	
		Add-R-ResStay	$\text{Add-R-ResStay} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent}$	0	$\text{ThresholdTimeSpent} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent}$	
	Perception	LS1 :Sensing	ExampleVisit	$1 - (\text{ExampleVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	1
			ExampleStay	$1 - (\text{ExampleStay} / \text{ThresholdStay})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdStay} / \text{ThresholdStay})$	1
IllustrationVisit			$1 - (\text{IllustrationVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	1	
IllustrationStay			$1 - (\text{IllustrationStay} / \text{ThresholdStay})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdStay} / \text{ThresholdStay})$	1	
ExerciseVisit			$1 - (\text{ExerciseVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	1	
ExerciseStay			$1 - (\text{ExerciseStay} / \text{ThresholdStay})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdStay} / \text{ThresholdStay})$	1	
LS2 :Intuitive		DefinitionVisit	$\text{DefinitionVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	0	$\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	
		DefinitionStay	$\text{DefinitionStay} / \text{ThresholdStay}$	0	$\text{ThresholdStay} / \text{ThresholdStay}$	
		Add-R-ResVisit	$\text{Add-R-ResVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	0	$\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	
		Add-R-ResStay	$\text{Add-R-ResStay} / \text{ThresholdStay}$	0	$\text{ThresholdStay} / \text{ThresholdStay}$	
		Add-R-ResVisit	$\text{Add-R-ResVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	0	$\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	
		Add-R-ResStay	$\text{Add-R-ResStay} / \text{ThresholdStay}$	0	$\text{ThresholdStay} / \text{ThresholdStay}$	
Input	LS1 :Visual	IllustrationVisit	$1 - (\text{IllustrationVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	1	
		IllustrationStay	$1 - (\text{IllustrationStay} / \text{ThresholdStay})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdStay} / \text{ThresholdStay})$	1	
	LS2 :Verbal	ForumVisit	$\text{ForumVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	0	$\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	
		ForumPost	$\text{ForumPost} / \text{ThresholdPost}$	0	$\text{ThresholdPost} / \text{ThresholdPost}$	
		ForumStay	$\text{ForumStay} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent}$	0	$\text{ThresholdTimeSpent} / \text{ThresholdTimeSpent}$	
		Add-R-ResVisit	$\text{Add-R-ResVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	0	$\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit}$	
		Add-R-ResStay	$\text{Add-R-ResStay} / \text{ThresholdStay}$	0	$\text{ThresholdStay} / \text{ThresholdStay}$	
LS	OutlineVisit	$1 - (\text{OutlineVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	$1 - (\text{ThresholdVisit} / \text{ThresholdVisit})$	1		

		$OutlineStay$	$1 - (OutlineStay / ThresholdStay)$	$1 - (ThresholdStay / ThresholdStay)$	1
		$ResumeVisit$	$ResumeVisit / ThresholdVisit$	0	$ThresholdVisit / ThresholdVisit$
	LS2 : Global	$ResumeStay$	$ResumeStay / ThresholdStay$	0	$ThresholdStay / ThresholdStay$

Table B.1: The proposed relationship between the metrics and the FSLSM dimensions. (In the context of learners)